

**REVIEW ON SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF HIV SAFETY
AMONG YOUNG PEOPLE**

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Annotation: This article discusses the key socio-psychological aspects of HIV safety among young people, such as the influence of the social environment, psychological barriers, and the role of education. The issue of HIV infection remains one of the most pressing concerns for the global community, particularly regarding young people, who represent the most vulnerable group due to their specific social and psychological characteristics.

Keywords: HIV, youth, safe behavior, prevention

**ОБЗОР СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ АСПЕКТОВ ВИЧ-
БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ МОЛОДЫХ ЛЮДЕЙ**

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются ключевые социально-психологические аспекты ВИЧ-безопасности среди молодёжи, такие как влияние социальной среды, психологические барьеры и роль образования. Проблема ВИЧ-инфекции остаётся одной из самых актуальных для мировой общественности, особенно в отношении молодёжи, которая представляет собой наиболее уязвимую группу по причине своих специфических социальных и психологических особенностей.

Ключевые слова: ВИЧ, молодежь, безопасное поведение, профилактика

YOSHLAR ORASIDA OIV-XAVFSIZLIGINING IJTIMOYIY- PSIXOLOGIK ASPEKTLARI SHARHI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yoshlar o'rtasida OIV xavfsizligi bilan bog'liq asosiy ijtimoiy-psixologik jihatlar, masalan, ijtimoiy muhitning ta'siri, psixologik to'siqlar va ta'limning roli ko'rib chiqiladi. OIV-infeksiyasi masalasi jahon jamoatchiligi uchun eng dolzarb masalalardan biri bo'lib qolmoqda. Ayniqsa yoshlar o'zlarining maxsus ijtimoiy va psixologik xususiyatlari sababli eng himoyasiz guruhni tashkil etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: HIV, yoshlar, xavfsiz xulq-atvor, profilaktika

Introduction. The issue of HIV infection remains one of the most pressing concerns for the global community, particularly regarding young people, who represent the most vulnerable group due to their specific social and psychological characteristics. HIV safety involves not only the physical barriers, such as condom use, but also the ability to make informed decisions and be aware of risks, which largely depends on socio-psychological factors.

The Influence of the Social Environment on HIV-Safe Behavior

The social environment of a young person significantly influences their attitudes toward sexuality, sexual practices, and personal safety. Key social institutions such as family, school, and the media play a crucial role in shaping young people's behavior and norms regarding HIV infection.

1. Family. The family is the first source of social and moral orientation. However, in some cases, traditional attitudes related to the taboo of discussing sexuality and sexual health may restrict young people from accessing important information about HIV (Aleshina, 2020). Research shows that in families where sexual education is openly discussed, young people are better informed about HIV protection methods and tend to exhibit more responsible behavior (Petrova, 2018).

2. Peers. During adolescence, peer opinions often become the primary reference point for sexual matters. Peer pressure can either increase or reduce risk levels

depending on the social norms within the group. Young people are often inclined to imitate the behavior of their peers, which can lead to neglecting precautionary measures if issues of sexual safety are not commonly discussed within the group (Kiseleva, 2019).

3. Media. Modern media (including the internet and social networks) plays a contradictory role in shaping attitudes toward sexual safety. On one hand, the availability of information about HIV and its transmission routes can be an effective tool for prevention (Smirnov, 2021). On the other hand, the media often emphasize sexuality as a source of pleasure, which may reduce the perception of potential risks (Nikolaeva, 2022). It is also important to note that myths about HIV are widely spread on the internet, which further complicates the situation.

Psychological Barriers and Risk Perception

Psychological factors often play a significant role in how young people perceive the risks associated with HIV:

1. Illusion of Invulnerability. Young people often perceive themselves as "invulnerable" and do not think about the long-term consequences of their actions (Kovalchuk, 2017). This is related to the psychological characteristics of adolescence, where a high susceptibility to stress and experimentation coexists with a lack of readiness to assess risks consciously.

2. Risk Ignorance. During adolescence, emotional and impulsive decisions may lead to ignoring clear threats. Psychological studies show that young people often underestimate the likelihood of contracting HIV, especially if they do not have direct experience with the disease (Grigorieva, 2018).

3. Social Stereotypes. Many adolescents and young people perceive HIV as a problem that affects only certain social groups, such as drug addicts or sexual minorities, which also contributes to the neglect of potential risks and reduces awareness (Timofeeva, 2020).

The Role of Educational and Preventive Programs

Effective HIV prevention among young people requires educational efforts aimed at developing responsible decision-making and safe behavior skills.

1. Sexual Education Programs. Effective educational programs should address both the theoretical and practical aspects of sexual education. Programs that emphasize the right of each person to protect their health and use contraception are more effective in changing behavior (Leonova, 2021). It is crucial for such programs to not only include information on HIV transmission routes but also to develop decision-making skills in the context of personal safety.

2. Psychological Counseling and Support. To overcome psychological barriers, such as the illusion of invulnerability, it is important to organize consultations and training sessions that help young people understand the consequences of risky behavior and learn how to take care of their health. Psychological training and awareness-raising courses can significantly reduce the level of HIV infection (Smirnov, 2019).

3. The Role of Interactive Learning Methods. Modern learning methods, such as role-playing games, simulations, and case studies, help young people work through real-life situations and learn how to apply the knowledge they have gained. Studies show that such approaches increase the engagement and awareness of participants (Rudenko, 2020).

Conclusion

Social-psychological aspects of HIV safety play a key role in preventing infection among young people. It is essential to create comprehensive programs that take into account not only biological but also psychological, social, and cultural factors influencing risk perception. Education and psycho-emotional support can significantly reduce the level of HIV infection among youth, fostering the development of healthy and responsible behavior patterns.

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